

Proceedings

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Toward an Intelligent Society: Challenges & Opportunities”

University Fehmi Agani Gjakove, Kosovo
22-23 May 2026

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Proceedings

**“Toward an Intelligent Society: Challenges & Opportunities”
International & Interdisciplinary Conference:**

21st International Conference of AIS-ALBSA & Institutional Partners

**6th Annual Conference of Center for School Leadership (CSL – AADF)
&**

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Tirana-Albania: 15 June 2007

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Tirana-Albania: 21 November 2006; Tirana International Hotel

Contents:

I.	Scientific Committee and Local Organizing Committee.....	4
II.	General Conference Program.....	6
III.	Next International & Interdisciplinary Conference.....	9
IV.	Abstracts Book & Full Papers.....	11
	4 th Peace Studies Forum of UPF & AIS	11
	Midterm Conference of the Balkan Sociological Forum, marking its 15 th Anniversary	17
	6 th Conference of School Leadership (CSL – AADF).....	28
	“Toward an Intelligent Society: Challenges & Opportunities” (21 st Annual International & Interdisciplinary Conference	57
	TS 01. Culture, Arts, Public Sphere and Communication	
	TS 02. Population, Migration and Diaspora	
	TS 03. Education and Sport	
	TS 04. Politics, Democracy, Integration and Law	
	TS 05. Religion, Collective Behavior and Social Movements	
	TS 06. Marriage, Family, Welfare, Social Policy and Community	
	TS 07. Childhood, Youth, Leisure, Aging and Gender	
	TS 08. Work, Professions and Organization	
	TS 09. Comparative, Historical, Regional, Global and Future Studies	
	TS 10. Security, Public Health, Deviance and Social Control	
	TS 11. Ethnic Relations, Nationalism, Human Rights	
	TS 12. Environment, Economy, Tourism and Development	
	TS 13. Science, Technology, Digitalization and Innovation	
V.	Index – Presenters & Contributors.....	388

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GIRLS' AND WOMEN'S EDUCATION IN ALBANIA (1912-1939)

Trends, Inequalities, and the Development of Women's Agency

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the development of girls' and women's primary education in Albania during the period 1912-1939, combining descriptive statistical analysis with a theoretically informed interpretation. Drawing on enrolment data from selected academic years (1919-1920, 1926-1927, and 1935-1936), the study identifies trends in girls' participation and patterns of gender inequality across educational levels. The findings reveal a gradual increase in girls' enrolment over time, rising from approximately 10.7% in 1919-1920 to nearly 29.4% in 1935-1936. However, this expansion was uneven and did not translate into equal participation at higher levels of education, where girls remained significantly underrepresented. The analysis is framed through the capability approach (Sen, 2011), which emphasizes the distinction between formal access to education and the expansion of real opportunities. In this context, the findings suggest that while educational provision improved, structural and socio-cultural constraints limited the realization of women's agency. The study contributes to the understanding of the relationship between education, gender, and development by demonstrating that

increased access does not necessarily imply equal opportunity, particularly in historically constrained social contexts.

Key words: *girls' education; women's education; gender inequality; educational access; capability approach; women's agency; Albania; historical analysis*

INTRODUCTION

The declaration of Albania's independence in 1912 marked the beginning of a complex and multidimensional state-building process, in which education was widely regarded as a fundamental instrument for nation-building and social development (Nathanaili, 2025).

In a context characterized by high levels of illiteracy and the absence of a consolidated educational infrastructure, the establishment of a national education system represented a major challenge for state institutions (Fischer, 1984). Within this framework, the inclusion of girls and women in education emerges as a key dimension for understanding not only the development of the education system, but also broader social and cultural transformations in Albanian society. On the one hand, women's education was closely linked to modernization efforts and the need to strengthen the country's human capital. On the other hand, it challenged deeply rooted traditional norms that confined women primarily to the private sphere (Durham, 1909; Elsie, 2010).

In this study, the concept of women's agency is explicitly grounded in the capability approach developed by Sen (2011: 210-225). Within this framework, agency refers to an individual's ability to pursue goals that they value and have reason to value. Education is understood as a key capability that enables the expansion of such agency, by increasing individuals' opportunities to make meaningful choices and participate in social life. However, the presence of educational institutions or formal access to schooling does not automatically translate into the expansion of agency. As highlighted by Sen (2011: 17) a distinction must be made between formal opportunities and real freedoms. This distinction is particularly relevant in contexts where socio-cultural constraints, such as patriarchal norms, limit the effective use of available opportunities. In this way, the study seeks to contribute to a deeper understanding of the relationship between education, gender, and development in the Albanian context.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This study aims to analyse the development of women's educational rights in Albania during the period 1912-1939. The theoretical framework of this study is grounded in the capability approach, which conceptualizes development as the expansion of individuals' real freedoms and opportunities rather than merely economic growth (Sen, 2011; Robeyns, 2017). Within this perspective, women are not viewed as passive beneficiaries of public policies, but as active agents capable of shaping their own life trajectories. Education plays a central role in this process, as it enhances individuals' capabilities and expands their opportunities for participation in social, economic, and political life (Nussbaum, 2000). However, the extent to which education contributes to the development of women's agency depends significantly on the broader socio-cultural context, particularly gender norms and institutional structures.

In societies characterized by strong patriarchal systems, women's access to resources, including education, is often mediated by social norms and power relations. Kandiyoti (1988) conceptualizes this dynamic as a process of "bargaining with patriarchy," where

women's opportunities are negotiated within existing gender hierarchies. Similarly, Walby (1990) emphasizes that patriarchy operates through both private and public structures, shaping women's access to education and participation in public life.

In the Albanian context, anthropological and historical studies highlight the persistence of gendered social structures that limited women's autonomy and participation beyond the domestic sphere (Durham, 1909; Fischer, 1984; Young, 2000; Elsie, 2010). These norms influenced not only everyday life but also educational access, where boys were systematically prioritized over girls. At the same time, state-building efforts and educational reforms created new institutional opportunities for expanding schooling (Vickers, 1999). However, the gap between formal policies and actual participation remained significant, reflecting a broader tension between institutional development and socio-cultural constraints.

From a capability perspective, this gap illustrates a situation in which formal educational opportunities exist, but are not fully translated into real freedoms for girls. Therefore, analysing girls' education in Albania during this period requires an integrated approach that combines statistical evidence with socio-cultural and institutional analysis.

METHODOLOGY

This study employs a descriptive historical approach, combining statistical analysis with institutional and socio-cultural interpretation. The methodological design is informed by the capability approach, which emphasizes the distinction between formal opportunities and actual outcomes (Sen, 2011). This conceptual distinction is central to the analysis of girls' education in Albania during this period, where increased enrolment does not necessarily imply equal opportunities for educational progression.

Due to the fragmented nature of historical data, the analysis follows a selective and indicator-based strategy. Rather than relying on a continuous time series, the study focuses on specific academic years for which comparable data are available. The academic year 1919-1920 is used as a baseline, as it provides detailed enrolment data disaggregated by gender and prefecture. The year 1926-1927 is included because it offers additional enrolment data disaggregated by educational level, enabling comparison between primary and secondary education. Finally, the academic year 1930-1931 is used to capture developments in educational infrastructure, particularly the expansion of schools and the presence of female teaching staff.

The analysis is structured around three main dimensions: (1) gender disparities in enrolment, (2) differences across educational levels, and (3) institutional development over time. Given the absence of consistent data across all years, trends are not interpreted as continuous statistical series but as indicative patterns based on available evidence.

Importantly, the capability approach informs not only the interpretation of results but also the selection of indicators. Enrolment data are used as a proxy for access to education, while differences across levels of education are interpreted as indicators of unequal opportunities for progression. Similarly, the expansion of schools and teaching staff is analysed as an institutional condition that may enable, but does not guarantee, the realization of educational opportunities for girls.

This integrated approach allows the study to move beyond a purely descriptive account and to interpret statistical patterns in relation to broader social and structural constraints.

The dataset used in this study is based on a previously published monograph by one

of the authors (Nathanaili, V., 2016). While the original work focused on the general development of the Albanian education system, the present article offers a new and joint analytical perspective by examining the data through the lens of gender inequality and the capability approach.

Research questions

- What was the extent of gender disparity in school enrolment in Albania in 1919-1920, 1926-1927 and 1935-1936?
- What patterns of inequality can be observed in girls' access to and progression within the education system?
- To what extent can the expansion of educational provision be interpreted as an expansion of real opportunities for girls and women in light of socio-cultural constraints?

DATA AND DISCUSSION

Gender disparity in school enrolment in Albania in 1919-1920, 1926-1927 and 1935-1936

The analysis of enrolment data across the academic years 1919-1920, 1926-1927, and 1935-1936 reveals a clear upward trend in girls' participation in primary education in Albania (Figure 1). During the Austro-Hungarian administration (1916-1918), primary education was made compulsory for children aged 7 to 14, corresponding to a seven-year cycle, as reflected in early post-independence educational regulations. This structure was later revised through the Organic Law on Education (1929), which standardised primary education into a six-year cycle and redefined compulsory schooling for children aged 6 to 13.

In 1919-1920, girls represented approximately 10.7% of total enrolment, indicating extremely limited access to education. By 1926-1927, their participation in primary education increased to approximately 19.1% (5,092 girls out of 26,612 pupils), reflecting a significant expansion in access. This trend continued in 1935-1936, when girls accounted

Figure 1: *Girls' share of total school enrolment in Albania (1919-1920, 1926-1927, and 1935-1936)*

for approximately 29.4% of primary school total enrolment (15,612 girls out of 53,041 pupils). Although boys continued to constitute the majority of students, the increase in girls' participation over time suggests a gradual but substantial shift towards greater inclusion. Despite this progress, gender disparities remained evident, as girls consistently represented less than one-third of total enrolment. These findings indicate that the expansion of education in Albania during this period was accompanied by increasing, yet still incomplete, gender inclusion. Regional variations persisted in 1935-1936, with prefectures such as Korçë and Gjirokastrë showing relatively higher levels of female participation, while others continued to exhibit more limited inclusion.

Patterns of inequality

While the increase in girls' enrolment over time indicates a positive trend, a closer examination reveals persistent and structured patterns of inequality within the education system.

a) Inequality in access

Although girls' participation increased between 1919 and 1936, they remained consistently underrepresented compared to boys, particularly beyond the primary level. This suggests that access was expanding in formal terms but remained uneven in practice. The data indicate a gradual increase in girls' enrolment; however, this expansion remained unequal, with girls continuing to be underrepresented relative to boys, especially at higher levels of education.

b) Inequality in progression

Where grade-level data are available, a clear pattern of attrition emerges: girls' participation declines significantly in higher grades. This indicates that even when access was secured, sustained participation was limited. A clear pattern of attrition is observed, with girls' participation decreasing across successive grades, pointing to structural barriers affecting their progression within the education system.

c) Inequality by type of education

The 1929 Organic Law on Education provides further evidence that the expansion of girls' education was shaped by gendered expectations.

Article 65: In Female Normal Schools, the subjects listed in Article 63 are taught, with the exception of political economy, which is substituted by domestic economy and household work, along with manual work conducted through specialized methods of sewing, cutting, and embroidery.

By introducing a differentiated curriculum for female students, the law reinforced traditional roles, thereby limiting the extent to which educational expansion translated into equal opportunities. Girls were more likely to be enrolled in vocational or gendered forms of education (e.g., sewing, domestic skills), while boys were more present in academic tracks. This reflects a gendered structuring of educational opportunities. The distribution of girls across educational tracks suggests a gendered division, with girls more frequently channelled into vocational or domestic-oriented training, reinforcing traditional gender roles.

d) Hidden inequality

Even where quantitative indicators show improvement, underlying socio-cultural constraints continued to shape participation patterns, limiting the depth and impact of these gains. Thus, apparent progress in enrolment figures may conceal persistent forms of inequality embedded in social norms and expectations.

Expansion of educational provision and real opportunities

The expansion of education during this period can be analysed by distinguishing between formal provision and real opportunities, particularly in light of socio-cultural constraints. Evidence from the academic years 1937-1938 and 1938-1939 (Nathanaili, 2016, pp. 234-236) provides concrete indications of the expansion of literacy courses as a central priority of the Ministry of Education. According to the Ministry's report, these courses were implemented "for the first time on such a scale," with 30 courses for women (1,900 participants) and 96 courses for men (approximately 3,000 participants). However, the structure and content of these courses reveal important gender differences. While both men and women were included, women's courses, particularly those focused on manual work, were explicitly oriented towards domestic preparation. The curriculum included hygiene, childcare, household management, sewing (hand and machine), dress cutting, embroidery, knitting, and basic knowledge of diseases, especially epidemic ones. Furthermore, the involvement of midwives, doctors, and local figures in delivering lectures on everyday life and family-related issues indicates that these courses were designed not only to reduce illiteracy but also to shape women's roles as mothers and household managers. The stated aim of forming "careful mothers and emancipated women" reflects a specific model of female education that combined literacy with domestic responsibility.

Additional evidence from 1938 further illustrates how efforts to expand female education were closely intertwined with gendered expectations. Within the broader framework of anti-illiteracy initiatives, the Singer Sewing Machine Company requested permission from the Ministry of Education to use school classrooms during summer holidays to organise free sewing courses for girls and women (Nathanaili, 2016, p. 238). This request was officially approved by Minister A. Dibra, who, on 22 July 1938, issued a circular to education inspectors instructing schools to provide one or two classrooms for this purpose, under the condition that any damages would be covered by the company. While they expanded access to training opportunities for women, their content was explicitly oriented towards domestic and gender-specific skills. This indicates that institutional support for female education extended beyond formal schooling and involved cooperation with private actors, yet continued to reinforce traditional gender roles. Thus, even as educational provision widened, the nature of the opportunities offered remained shaped by prevailing socio-cultural expectations.

CONCLUSIONS

These findings suggest that, although educational provision expanded significantly in quantitative terms, the opportunities offered to women remained structured within clearly defined gender roles. While the proportion of girls in school enrolment increased significantly over time, this growth did not eliminate gender disparities. Girls remained consistently underrepresented, particularly at higher levels of education.

From a capability perspective (Sen, 2011), these findings highlight an important distinction between formal access to education and the expansion of real opportunities. The observed increase in enrolment suggests that educational provision improved over time; however, the limited progression of girls to secondary education indicates that these opportunities were not equally accessible in practice. In this sense, the expansion of schooling can be interpreted as a partial enhancement of capabilities, rather than a full realization of women's agency.

This gap between access and progression is further illuminated when considered in light of socio-cultural constraints. Kandiyoti's (1988) concept of "bargaining with patriarchy" provides a useful framework for understanding how women's educational opportunities may be negotiated within family and societal structures. In contexts where gender roles are strongly defined, girls' education, especially beyond the primary level, may be perceived as less necessary or even undesirable. As a result, even when schools are available, the decision to continue education may be constrained by social expectations and power relations within the household. The Albanian case reflects this dynamic. While state-building efforts and educational expansion created new institutional opportunities, these were embedded within a broader social context characterized by patriarchal norms. Consequently, the increase in girls' enrolment did not automatically translate into sustained participation or equal educational outcomes. The findings therefore suggest that the development of girls' education in Albania during this period should be understood as a process of partial and uneven inclusion. Educational expansion improved access, but structural and cultural barriers continued to limit girls' ability to fully benefit from these opportunities.

Overall, this study demonstrates the importance of combining statistical analysis with a theoretically informed interpretation. By integrating the capability approach with insights from gender theory, it becomes possible to move beyond descriptive trends and to better understand the underlying mechanisms shaping educational inequality.

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